

The Role of Education in Reducing Poverty in Ghana

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Introduction

Education is widely recognized as a fundamental driver of socioeconomic development and poverty reduction. In Ghana, education has historically played a critical role in shaping human capital and enhancing opportunities for individuals and communities. From the early international education efforts in the 1730s to contemporary policies such as the Free Senior High School (SHS) initiative, the country has consistently sought to improve access, quality, and equity in education. Despite these efforts, significant challenges remain, including disparities in rural and urban education, gender gaps, inadequate resources, and barriers faced by children with disabilities. Research has shown that higher levels of educational attainment correlate with increased earnings, improved household welfare, and enhanced social mobility. Education also supports skills development, entrepreneurship, and civic engagement, all of which contribute to breaking the cycle of intergenerational poverty in Ghana.

The main research question guiding this study is:

“How does education contribute to reducing poverty in Ghana, and what mechanisms link educational attainment to improved socioeconomic outcomes?” The objectives of the essay are:

1. To examine the relationship between different levels of education (primary, secondary, tertiary, and vocational) and poverty reduction in Ghana.
2. To explore how access to education influences household income, employment opportunities, and social mobility.
3. To identify the challenges and barriers that prevent equitable access to quality education, particularly for girls, children with disabilities, and rural populations.
4. To analyze the role of government policies and programs, such as Free SHS, vocational training, and literacy initiatives, in promoting poverty alleviation.
5. To provide recommendations for strengthening education as a sustainable tool for reducing poverty in Ghana.

Methodology

This research article relies on an approach based on secondary data analysis. My essay examines existing literature, policy documents, government reports, and academic publications to explore how education contributes to poverty reduction in Ghana. By reviewing sources from organizations such as AACRAO, UNESCO, UNICEF, EDU-Port Japan, and various scholarly authors, the study identifies patterns, arguments, and evidence that link access to education with socio-economic outcomes.

The method involves thematic analysis: grouping information into key themes such as access to basic education, vocational training, gender disparities, government reforms, and socio-economic impacts. This approach allows for a deeper understanding of how educational policies and systems shape poverty outcomes. Since the Article is based entirely on document analysis and does not involve interviews or human participants, no field research is required. The methodology is appropriate for a short research proposal because it provides a clear, systematic way to analyze existing knowledge and identify gaps for future researches .

Abstract

This Article examines the role of education in reducing poverty in Ghana by exploring the historical development of the educational system, the relationship between educational attainment and income, and the impact of government policies and programs. It highlights how primary, secondary, tertiary, and vocational education contribute to improving household welfare, social mobility, and economic empowerment, particularly among disadvantaged groups such as girls, rural populations, and children with disabilities. The essay also analyzes challenges, including disparities in access, quality of education, and infrastructure limitations, which hinder the full potential of education in alleviating poverty. Findings indicate that policies such as Free Senior High School (SHS), adult literacy programs, and vocational training have significantly contributed to reducing poverty, though gaps remain. Based on these findings, the essay recommends expanding access to quality education, promoting inclusive and gender-sensitive policies, integrating digital literacy, and strengthening teacher training and school resources. Overall, education is identified as a crucial tool for breaking the cycle of intergenerational poverty and fostering sustainable development in Ghana.

Linking Education and Poverty Reduction in Ghana: Historical and Policy Perspectives

Ghana, with a population of 34.7 million in 2024, has a long tradition of international education dating back to the 1730s, when Ghanaians who studied in Europe returned home and helped introduce formal education¹. The relationship between education and poverty can generally be understood in two major ways. First, spending on education helps build the skills and productivity of low-income households. This leads to higher earnings and improves overall living conditions and human development. Second, poverty itself creates significant barriers to educational success. It influences educational outcomes in three key areas. In his master's thesis, *Poverty and Development: Role of Education in Poverty Reduction in the Ada East District of Ghana*, Augustine Addai-Boateng argues “ In Ghana, two-thirds of the non-agricultural working population is active in the informal economy, with many, particularly women, remaining persistently poor. The Education Act of 1987 and the 1992 Constitution created opportunities to reform educational policies, leading to a primary school enrollment rate of 84% by 2011, higher than the Sub-Saharan average. In 2016, free senior high school education was introduced to increase literacy, although gender and rural–urban disparities remain “². Consequently, a lack of education limits an individual's earning potential, and poverty can continue across subsequent generations within the same family. Richard Senna argues that Formal education equips individuals with knowledge, skills, and qualifications that increase their employability and income-earning potential. By acquiring education, individuals gain access to better job opportunities, higher-paying jobs, and improved economic prospects, which can help them escape poverty, and improve income levels leading to the overall improvement of the socioeconomic living conditions of people³. It is important to note that in Ghana, ‘education poverty’ (lack of education) and ‘income poverty’ are closely interconnected and reinforce one another. Limited education is a major driver of income poverty, while insufficient income makes it difficult to overcome educational deprivation. Additionally, education plays a crucial role in meeting basic needs and alleviating poverty, and access to basic needs often includes access to education. Thus, the provision of education and the fulfillment of basic needs mutually strengthen each other. While the inverse relationship between education and poverty is well recognized, there is ongoing debate regarding the specific impact of different levels of education. According to Kwabena Adu-Ababio and Robert Darko Osei, It is a known fact that Ghana is one of the countries in Africa that spends a higher percentage of its total budget and GDP on education. Ghana's spending on education is among the highest in Africa comparing a global average of 5 per cent⁴. In Ghana, we define a variable called the “probability of being poor” based on the lowest income quintiles. This dummy variable takes a value of one if an individual belongs to the lowest quintile, indicating poverty, and zero if they are in higher quintiles, indicating non-poverty. This approach highlights the close link between limited education, low income, and poverty, reflecting how educational deprivation contributes to persistent poverty in Ghana. A GPE partner since 2004, [Ghana](#) has made impressive progress in growing its economy, reducing poverty and improving education. It has enrolled all children in at least two years of preschool and sends as many girls as boys to school at all levels But Ghana is one of the few countries with a two-year preschool policy as part of its commitment to Free and

¹ American Association of Collegiate Registrars and Admissions Officers (AACRAO), “Ghana,” *AACRAO*

² Augustine Addai-Boateng, *Poverty and Development: Role of Education in Poverty Reduction in the Ada East District of Ghana* (Master's thesis, Faculty of Landscape and Society (LANDSAM), 2019). P.7 – 8

³ Richard Senna, “The Role of Formal Education for Poverty Reduction and Development in the Digital Era: A Study of Sogakope, South Tongu District, Ghana,” *International Journal of Educational Qualitative Quantitative Research*, no. 2 (2023) p. 39

⁴ Kwabena Adu-Ababio and Robert Darko Osei, *Effects of an Education Reform on Household Poverty and Inequality: A Microsimulation Analysis on the Free Senior High School Policy in Ghana*, WIDER Working Paper 2018/147 (Helsinki: UNU-WIDER, 2018). P. 3

Compulsory Basic Education, which places it ahead of the curve compared to other countries in sub-Saharan Africa.⁵

Educational Attainment and Economic Empowerment in Ghana

Another important aspect of education's role in reducing poverty in Ghana is the direct and positive relationship between educational attainment and earnings. In his study on education in Sogakope, Richard Senna argues that Formal education that utilises technology is expected to encourage individual progress to innovate, these factors are steps in efforts to break the chain of poverty. The educated young generation based on technology has great potential to create creative solutions to global challenges and contribute to sustainable development. To realise this young generation, significant investment is needed in aspects of equitable digital infrastructure, affordable internet access, and an inclusive curriculum relevant to the technological era's needs .⁶ Therefore, it is clear that education can enhance the earning potential of the poor in Ghana, making them more productive and economically empowered. Post-primary education initially developed through seminaries and teacher training colleges, and in 1876, Mfantshipim School was founded as the first secondary school. Demand for higher education grew during the colonial period, often exceeding what British officials provided⁷ . A higher educational level of the household head in Ghana significantly lowers the likelihood of the household experiencing poverty . Kwabena Adu-Ababio and Robert Darko Osei emphasized that With the rising need and awareness to educate, it is the dream of every parent or guardian to see their ward attain some secondary education. The problem however is that, although it is an undebatable fact that private schools are the most expensive, public secondary schools which outnumber the latter and should be accessible to all are quite expensive for the average Ghanaian to attend⁸. In Ghana, providing access to education can break this cycle by increasing earnings and helping households meet their basic needs . According to Richard Senna , education fights poverty in two ways. First, it leads to more money directly by giving people better job options and higher salaries. Second, it helps people live better lives indirectly by improving their overall standards of living⁹ . In Ghana, poverty is not only concentrated in households with illiterate or less-educated heads, but it also tends to affect female-headed households more severely than male-headed ones. Addai-Boateng argues that , Ghana is one of the Sub-Saharan African countries that has been noted in the last two decades for its remarkable improvement in economic growth and poverty reduction, stability, good governance and relatively well-developed institutional capacities that support the gradual achievement of sustainable development. The country was the first within the Sub-Saharan African regions to reduce poverty rate by half from 56.5% to 24.2% between 1991 and 2012, a rate which was less than half the African average of 43%¹⁰ .

In Ghana, different educational levels—primary, secondary, and tertiary—play a crucial role in raising household per capita expenditure. Since these expenditures include non-food items, education is also important for improving overall household welfare. According to Richard Senna, education is a critical form of human capital investment, capable of influencing individual income levels and, by extension, poverty rates¹¹. It would be incorrect to assume that poverty reduction, growth, and development can wait until primary education is universal. Efforts should also focus on post-primary

⁵ Global Partnership for Education, "Ghana: Making Quality Education Available to More Children," Global Partnership,

⁶ Senna, "The Role of Formal Education," p .35

⁷ AACRAO, "Ghana."

⁸ Adu-Ababio and Osei, *Effects of an Education Reform*, p .3

⁹ Senna, "The Role of Formal Education," p . 40

¹⁰ Addai-Boateng, *Poverty and Development*, P.5

¹¹ Senna, "The Role of Formal Education," p.35

education, which plays an equally important role. While primary education provides the foundational level of human capital, secondary and higher education, along with investments in science and technology, drive faster and more sustained economic growth and development. Evidence from India indicates that illiteracy, literacy, and primary education are associated with higher poverty rates, whereas middle and secondary education are linked to lower poverty levels. In her study on gender and poverty, Mariama Awumbila emphasizes that Poor people themselves do not remain idle or passive in their experience of poverty. Among coping and adaptive strategies adopted in Ghana are the mutual exchanges of goods and services, remittances and direct handouts, borrowing and lending¹². In Ghana, it has been observed that individuals with lower levels of education face a higher likelihood of living in poverty. According to Addai-Boateng, Lack of education can thus be considered a form of poverty. Both absolute and relative poverty affect educational opportunities: absolute poverty limits school attendance due to financial constraints, while relative poverty can cause social exclusion. This exclusion may reduce the ability to fully benefit from education. Consequently, education and poverty are closely linked beyond just income measures¹³. As education expands in Ghana, the number of individuals with higher education and higher earnings increases, and the overall educational level of the labor force improves; however, the growth of highly educated, high-earning individuals can also contribute to greater income inequality. Again Richard Senna argues that, individuals can obtain better jobs and access broader economic opportunities, which in turn can help lift them out of poverty. Education also contributes to social mobility, enabling individuals to move from lower to higher social status. In the context of development, formal education supports human resource development by improving people's skills and capacities. This contributes to sustainable economic growth, improving health and well-being, and strengthening social engagement and democracy¹⁴.

Bridging Rural-Urban Poverty Gaps Through Inclusive and Quality Education

In Ghana, a logistic regression model was estimated to examine the “probability of being poor” based on work experience and varying levels of education. According to Awumbila Other poverty reduction programmes have been targeted specifically at women, to improve access to technology and credit for women, to reduce the existing gaps in education, especially in science and technology, as well as the passage of various laws criminalizing certain negative cultural practices and protecting the rights of women and children in inheritance issues¹⁵. In Ghana, as educational attainment rises, the probability of being poor declines proportionally, as illustrated in the figure. Augustine Addai-Boateng argues that, Despite this significant achievement, the annual rate of poverty reduction has been quite slow comparing its average of 1.8% per year during the 1990s to its average of 1.1% per year from the year 2006¹⁶. In Ghana, both work experience and all levels of education are negatively associated with the poverty status of employed individuals. Furthermore, as the level of education attained increases, the probability of being poor consistently decreases in proportion. According to Emmanuel Intsiful and Albert Martins, Poverty includes not only economic hardship but also psychological factors such as shame, discrimination, and lack of power. In rural Ghana, adult education programs focus on vocational

¹² Mariama Awumbila, “Gender Equality and Poverty in Ghana: Implications for Poverty Reduction Strategies,” *Springer Science+Business Media B.V.*, published online February 14, 2007 p.158

¹³ Addai-Boateng, *Poverty and Development*, P.10

¹⁴ Senna, “The Role of Formal Education,” p.42

¹⁵ Awumbila, “Gender Equality and Poverty in Ghana,” p.158

¹⁶ Addai-Boateng, *Poverty and Development*, P.5

and agricultural training to equip adults with employable skills and reduce poverty. Non-formal education is a deliberate government effort to improve the lives of rural populations. Government-led poverty reduction also relies on equitable resource distribution through strong local governance, democratic participation, and active civil society. Adult literacy programs therefore empower individuals and create broader positive development within the entire community¹⁷. Education equips Ghanaians with the skills and knowledge needed to secure better-paying jobs, reducing the cycle of poverty. According to Richard Baah-Mintah, Ellen Owusu-Adjei, and Frederick Koomson, Small-scale industries in Ghana play a significant role in economic development and poverty reduction. Promoting these enterprises, particularly through education and training, increases entrepreneurs' productivity and profitability, thereby reducing poverty levels. To support this, institutions such as the Business Advisory Centre (BAC) of the National Board for Small Scale Industries (NBSSI), Ghana Appropriate Technology Services (GRATIS), and the Microfinance and Small Loan Centre (MASLOC) provide educational and training services to entrepreneurs. In the Nkoranza South municipality, the BAC is primarily responsible for offering relevant information, education, training, and guidance to small-scale entrepreneurs to enhance their business performance and reduce poverty¹⁸. Access to quality education empowers individuals to start small businesses, fostering economic independence. Joe Adu-Agyem and Patrick Osei-Poku emphasized that, To achieve the objectives of tertiary education, the wellbeing and economic development of the country, it is very crucial to strengthen all the various levels of the country's educational system by remedying all anomalies and deficiencies to ensure quality education delivery in the system¹⁹. Literacy programs in rural Ghana help communities understand and utilize financial resources more effectively. Education in Ghana dates back to precolonial times. During this time, informal and indigenous education was the form of education that prevailed where knowledge and skills were passed on to the younger ones within the community by the elderly ones in the form of apprenticeship or by word of mouth²⁰. Education increases awareness of health and nutrition, which indirectly improves productivity and income. After independence in 1957, Ghana adopted a policy of education for all, recognizing education as essential for national development. The system resembled the British model but aimed for universal access. The 1950s and 1960s were considered a golden age of education, with schools expanding so rapidly that they were nicknamed "mushroom schools." By the 1990s, high school graduation rates had increased significantly, and today, approximately 450,000 students graduate annually. Ghanaian students continue to maintain strong academic competitiveness internationally²¹. By promoting gender equality in schools, education ensures that both boys and girls can contribute to economic growth. Richard Senna argues that formal education significantly impacts poverty reduction and community development. It establishes a positive correlation between educational attainment and improved economic prospects. The research highlights that quality education leads to better employment opportunities, higher income levels, and enhanced social and cultural development. Additionally, it emphasizes the critical role of household income in influencing children's educational achievements, with financial constraints posing significant barriers to accessing quality education²². Vocational and technical training prepares young Ghanaians for practical jobs in growing industries. According to Addai-Boateng, Undoubtedly,

¹⁷ Emmanuel Intsiful and Albert Martins, *Examining the Role of Non-Formal Education as a Conduit to Poverty Reduction and Rural Development: The Case of a Rural Community in a Municipality in Ghana* (unpublished manuscript, n.d.).p .7

¹⁸ Richard Baah-Mintah, Ellen Owusu-Adjei, and Frederick Koomson, "Education and Training of Small-Scale Entrepreneurs: A Tool for Poverty Reduction in the Nkoranza South Municipality, Ghana," *Journal of Business and Management Sciences* 6, no. 2 (2018) p .144

¹⁹ Joe Adu-Agyem and Patrick Osei-Poku, *Quality Education in Ghana: The Way Forward* (Kumasi, Ghana: Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology, 2012). P 169

²⁰ Addai-Boateng, *Poverty and Development*, P.2

²¹ AACRAO, "Ghana."

²² Senna, "The Role of Formal Education," p.42

the country has made significant progress with poverty reduction yet many of its people most especially in rural areas still live in extreme poverty. Poverty is more prevalent in the rural areas of Ghana than in urban areas. The average rate of poverty in the rural areas is 38.2% whereas that of the urban areas is 10.4% (World Bank, 2015)²³.

Educated citizens are more likely to participate in policy-making that supports poverty reduction strategies. Joe Adu-Agyem and Patrick Osei-Poku analysis that , In the present knowledge based economy, tertiary education plays an important role in the creation, dissemination and application of knowledge to meet developmental needs. It also has a role in the strengthening of the entire educational system and fostering synergies in the entire economy²⁴ . Education encourages innovation and entrepreneurship, creating new opportunities for local communities. In spite of the progress Ghana has made in improving access to education for all, there are still challenges preventing thousands of children from going to school and learning. The school environment is usually not conducive to learning. Classes are overcrowded, water and sanitation facilities are inadequate and trained teachers and school books are in short supply²⁵. Schools in impoverished areas provide a safe environment where children can learn rather than engage in child labor. In *Role of Education in Poverty Reduction in the Ada East District of Ghana*, Augustine Addai-Boateng Analysis that , Ghanaian education policies have aimed to eliminate illiteracy for over 40 years, highlighting the need to assess education's potential in reducing poverty, especially in rural areas like the Ada East Community. This study examines the relationship between education and poverty, focusing on community perceptions of education as a tool for poverty reduction, the influence of household income and parents' education on children's schooling, and the contributions of educational policymakers in alleviating poverty. The thesis includes literature review, theoretical framework, research methodology, study area details, findings, analysis, and policy²⁶ .

From Policy to Practice: Education as a Catalyst for Inclusive Development in Ghana

Long-term investment in education helps break intergenerational poverty by giving future generations better opportunities. The poor quality of education is reflected in students' results. Children living with disabilities face even more challenges and adolescent girls are often denied the chance to complete secondary education²⁷. Schools provide knowledge on financial literacy, helping families manage resources and escape poverty . According to Joe Adu-Agyem and Patrick Osei-Poku , The Technical and Vocational Education and Training sub-sector of the Ghanaian economy is supposed to help contribute much to the socio-economic development of the country²⁸ .Educated farmers can adopt modern agricultural techniques, increasing crop yields and household income. Addai-Boateng analysis that , According to the Ghana Living Standards Survey report by the Ghana Statistical Service (2017), 6.8 million Ghanaians, representing 23.4 percent of the population are considered poor or living in poverty as they cannot afford to spend more than GH¢4.82 approximately US\$1 a day in 2016/2017.²⁹

²³ Addai-Boateng, *Poverty and Development*, P.6

²⁴ Adu-Agyem and Osei-Poku, *Quality Education in Ghana*, 169

²⁵ United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF), "Education," UNICEF Ghana,

²⁶ Addai-Boateng, *Poverty and Development*, 7–8

²⁷ UNICEF, "Education."

²⁸ Adu-Agyem and Osei-Poku, *Quality Education in Ghana*, P. 169

²⁹ Addai-Boateng, *Poverty and Development*, 7–8. Addai-Boateng, *Poverty and Development*, P.6

Education fosters critical thinking, enabling Ghanaians to identify and take advantage of economic opportunities. Ghana, like many other African countries, is facing a learning crisis. In sub-Saharan Africa, learning poverty, defined as the share of children unable to read and understand an age-appropriate text by age 10, is estimated by the World Bank, UNESCO, and other organizations³⁰. By reducing illiteracy, education opens doors to formal employment and government jobs. Quality education in Ghana is a priority for the government, Ministry of Education, Ghana Education Service, and corporate bodies. It involves providing appropriate inputs and effective delivery to achieve excellent outcomes, aiming to develop well-rounded individuals intellectually, psychologically, spiritually, emotionally, physically, and intuitively³¹. Access to higher education creates a skilled workforce that attracts investment and stimulates local economies. According to UNICEF, Nearly 623,500 children of primary school age are still not enrolled in primary school and one out of four children in the kindergarten age range (from four to five years of age) are not in pre-school. According to the 2010 national census, 20 percent of children with physical disabilities are not attending school. Although Ghana has been successful at closing the gender gap when it comes to completing school at primary education level, it is still high at secondary level. Research shows that adolescent girls are usually unable to get an education due to factors such as poverty, gender inequality and long distances from school³². According to the International Institute for Capacity Building in Africa (IICBA), The Human Capital Index for Ghana shows that although most children survive past age five and are expected to complete about 12 years of schooling, the level of learning they achieve is low, resulting in only six learning-adjusted years of schooling. Additional indicators—such as a 77 percent adult survival rate and an 82 percent chance of not being stunted—reveal that overall human development outcomes limit future productivity. Based on these factors, a child born in Ghana today is projected to reach only 45 percent of their potential productivity³³. Educational programs promote social mobility, giving disadvantaged children a chance to improve their living standards. According to Addai-Boateng, it is an investment that has the potential of reaping great rewards with some externalities. Education has come out as a key prerequisite for poverty reduction and improving the living standards or livelihoods of developing countries including Ghana³⁴. Learning about civic rights helps citizens advocate for social programs that alleviate poverty. Children with disabilities often lose out on an education because they are ‘invisible’ in data and overlooked during the implementation of education programs. They are seldom counted as out-of-school or school going children. In the absence of conveniently located schools, disability-friendly infrastructure and learning environments, children with disabilities, have irregular attendance, long periods of absence and finally drop out.³⁵ Education supports women’s empowerment, allowing them to contribute financially to their families and communities. Awumbila Argues that , In Ghana, within the national economic framework, several initiatives have been taken towards poverty reduction. These strategies include the Program of Action to Mitigate the Social Cost of Adjustment (PAMSCAD), as well as the Ghana- Vision 2020, which had specific policy statements pertaining to poverty reduction. Subsequently, a range of development programmes, which weresector specific have had poverty reduction provisions. These include the free compulsory universal basic education (fCUBE) of the Ministry of Education, and the medium term agricultural development strategy (MTADP) of the Ministry of Food and Agriculture to mention a few. These culminated in the Ghana Poverty Reduction strategy (GPRS) which is the latest economic framework by the government and focuses on addressing poverty in a holistic way through a set of “comprehensive policies, strategies,

³⁰ International Institute for Capacity Building in Africa, “Ghana: Education Country Brief,” UNESCO IICBA,

³¹ Addai-Boateng, *Poverty and Development*, P.4 –5

³² UNICEF, “Education.”

³³ IICBA, “Ghana: Education Country Brief.”

³⁴ Addai-Boateng, *Poverty and Development*, P.13

³⁵ UNICEF, “Education.”

programmes, and projects to support growth and poverty reduction over a three-year period ³⁶ . Knowledge gained through education encourages sustainable practices that protect resources and long-term livelihoods.

From Kindergarten to Tertiary Education: Expanding Access and Opportunities to Break Poverty Cycles

American Association of Collegiate Registrars and Admissions Officers (AACRAO) argued that, Ghana's current educational system follows a 6-3-3-4 structure, consisting of six years of primary school, three years of junior high, three years of senior high, and four years at university. Private international secondary schools are gradually increasing in number, offering curricula such as Cambridge A-Levels, International Baccalaureate (IB), and U.S. high school programs ³⁷. Access to quality education in Ghana helps break the cycle of poverty across generations. EDU-Port Japan argued , kindergarten lasts for 2 years that the main aim is To introduce children to basic concepts in literacy and numeracy, social interaction, and personal hygiene , primary school 6 years and the Subjects include English, Mathematics, Science, Social Studies, and local languages. Additional subjects like Creative Arts and Physical Education are also part of the curriculum and the objective is To develop foundational skills in literacy, numeracy, and critical thinking, fostering a positive attitude towards learning³⁸ . Poverty in Ghana can be alleviated when education equips young people with vocational and technical skills. According to Addai-Boateng, The government seeks to provide quality education at all levels by ensuring adequate resources, facilities, and a healthy, safe, gender-sensitive learning environment. Effective education delivery includes trained and motivated teachers using child-centered approaches, skillful assessment, proper time management, positive attitudes towards learning, supervision, discipline, and the use of information and communication technology as a learning tool ³⁹ . The government of Ghana recognizes that education is key to tackling widespread poverty in rural areas . junior high schools lasts 3 years which the Subjects include English, Mathematics, Integrated Science, Social Studies, Basic Design and Technology, Information and Communication Technology (ICT), and local languages and the objectives are To consolidate primary education and prepare students for secondary education or vocational training ⁴⁰. Education in Ghana empowers communities to create small businesses, which reduces poverty locally. According to AACRAO analysis , The current system removed the distinction between post-secondary and tertiary education. Since 2004, all diploma- and degree-granting institutions are considered tertiary, and completion of senior high school allows entry into all tertiary programs, including technical colleges, teacher and nurse training, and universities. In 2020, the Ghana Tertiary Education Commission (GTEC) was formed to regulate and accredit public and private higher education institutions. As of 2024, Ghana has 307 tertiary institutions, half of which are public, enrolling 85% of the 635,000 students. Private tertiary education is rapidly growing, with over 65,000 undergraduates currently enrolled. Some programs show "expired" accreditation due to backlog renewals, but GTEC oversees updates and regulation ⁴¹.

Poverty rates in Ghana decline when children, especially girls, receive consistent access to education. According to EDU-Port Japan, The Secondary Education continue 3 years which includes general arts , general science , technical , vocational and agricultural . after that Senior High School (SHS) for 3 years that the objective is To prepare students for higher education or entry into the workforce by providing specialized knowledge and skills ⁴² . Education provides Ghanaians with knowledge about health, finance, and entrepreneurship, which helps fight poverty. AACRAO argues that , Before 1987, Ghana followed a British-based 6-5-2-3 system, including O-Levels and A-Levels. Middle schools

³⁶ Awumbila, "Gender Equality and Poverty in Ghana,"p.157

³⁷ AACRAO, "Ghana."

³⁸ OVERVIEW OF THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM IN GHANA," EDU-Port Japan, July 11, 2024,

³⁹ Addai-Boateng, *Poverty and Development*, P.4 –5

⁴⁰ EDU-Port Japan, "Overview of the Educational System in Ghana.

⁴¹ AACRAO, "Ghana."

⁴² EDU-Port Japan, "Overview of the Educational System in Ghana.

existed between primary and secondary education. O-Levels, representing eleven years of schooling, did not qualify students for university, while A-Levels allowed admission to tertiary institutions and sometimes advanced placement abroad. The SSSCE replaced A-Levels in 1993, and in 2006, it was replaced by the WASSCE, administered by the West African Examinations Council (WAEC) ⁴³. In Ghana, education initiatives targeting disadvantaged groups are essential for long-term poverty reduction. According to the American Association of Collegiate Registrars and Admissions Officers, University admission in Ghana depends solely on WASSCE aggregate scores, with competitive programs such as medicine or electrical engineering requiring very low aggregates (6–8). Students must complete senior high school and the WASSCE for eligibility; Ghana does not have a homeschool system, though private WASSCE candidates may claim otherwise. Vocational and technical certificates such as GBCE, ABCE, and City & Guilds do not grant university admission. English is the official language and the sole medium of instruction, and TOEFL is only required when English proficiency is not demonstrated through the WASSCE or other accepted tests⁴⁴. Poverty in Ghana remains a challenge, but expanding education opportunities is a proven solution. According to M. B. I. Omoniyi, There is also a positive feedback from improved education to greater income equality, which, in turn, is likely to favour higher rates of growth. As education becomes more broadly based, low-income people are better able to seek out economic opportunities⁴⁵. By investing in education, Ghana can equip its citizens to overcome poverty and contribute to national development. Richard Senna argues that, In the digital era, formal education plays a strategic role in equipping individuals and communities with the skills, knowledge, and digital literacy needed to thrive in the professional sphere. In addition, in the era of digital education, formal education is expected to open access to better economic opportunities and provide provisions for improving the quality of life of individuals and communities⁴⁶. Education in Ghana not only reduces poverty but also promotes social and economic equality. M. B. I. Omoniyi argue that, For example, a study of the relation between schooling, income inequality and poverty in 18 countries of Latin America in the 1990s found that one quarter of the variation in workers' incomes was accounted for by variations in schooling attainment; it concludes that 'clearly education is the variable with the strongest impact on income equality'⁴⁷. Poverty in Ghana is often linked to illiteracy, making education a critical tool for change. According to Kwabena Adu-Ababio and Robert Darko Osei, a Ghana where children will not be denied the opportunity of senior high school education because of the inability of their parents to support them financially. If free education means one thing, then it is the fact that the era where pupils dropped out from school for financial reasons, or had their education cut short, has become a thing of the past⁴⁸. Education programs in Ghana aim to give every child the chance to escape poverty through learning. Omoniyi argues that, Education may affect per capita income growth via its impact on the denominator, i.e. population growth. For example, a study of fourteen African countries for the mid-nineties showed a negative correlation between female schooling and fertility in almost all countries, with primary education having a negative impact in about half the countries and no significant effects in the other half, while secondary education invariably reduced fertility⁴⁹.

Increasing access to education in Ghana helps young people avoid poverty traps and improve their livelihoods. Caine Rolleston emphasizes that, In relation to the absolute poverty-reducing effect of educational expansion, the findings overall are somewhat ambiguous, but it is clear in equity terms that convex patterns of returns to education benefit the more advantaged disproportionately, increasing inequality and relative poverty, other things being equal⁵⁰. Kwabena Adu-Ababio and Robert Darko Osei argue that based on Ghana's 2013 Living Standards Survey and updated to 2017 policies, to

⁴³ AACRAO, "Ghana."

⁴⁴ AACRAO, "Ghana."

⁴⁵ M. B. I. Omoniyi, *The Role of Education in Poverty Alleviation and Economic Development: A Theoretical Perspective and Counselling Implications* (Akungba Akoko, Ondo State, Nigeria: Department of Guidance & Counselling, Adekunle Ajasin University, n.d.). p.179

⁴⁶ Senna, "The Role of Formal Education," p. 34

⁴⁷ Omoniyi, *The Role of Education in Poverty Alleviation*, p.179

⁴⁸ Adu-Ababio and Osei, *Effects of an Education Reform*, P. 14

⁴⁹ Omoniyi, *The Role of Education in Poverty Alleviation*, p.179

⁵⁰ Caine Rolleston, *Educational Access and Poverty Reduction: The Case of Ghana 1991–2006* (London: Institute of Education, University of London, 2011). P. 347

analyse taxes, social benefits, and indirect taxes. It models the Free SHS reform by assigning annual benefits of GHC1,002.47 to resident secondary students and GHC648.47 to non-residents, while households already receiving social interventions continue to benefit. A counterfactual scenario also gives GHC648.47 to extremely poor youths of secondary-school age who are not enrolled. The study examines financing the reform by increasing workers' social security contributions, which could generate revenue close to the reform's cost. Although indirect tax increases could also finance the policy, insufficient consumption data limits detailed modelling of such options⁵¹. Education in Ghana is a pathway for individuals and families to rise above poverty and achieve stability. According to Kwabena Adu-Ababio and Robert Darko Osei, It can be seen that the free SHS policy decreases overall poverty, as this is further amplified especially among households with children i.e. household members below 18 years. Although both overall poverty and poverty in households with children decrease by less than 1 percentage point, the fall in the latter (0.63 per cent) is slightly greater than that of the former (0.60 per cent)⁵². Many regions in Ghana face poverty, but education programs are creating new opportunities for growth. According to Lawrence Kofi Ameteepe and Dimitris Anastasiou, Public investment, not just in economic infrastructure (mainly cocoa and gold), but also in health and education, has been key to achieving human development. The fact that Ghana is a typical Sub-Saharan country, but also an example of heartening progress in terms of human wellbeing among developing countries, can make the study of its special and inclusive education a revelatory or heuristic case for Sub-Saharan Africa. Specifically, it poses the question of whether the status of special and inclusive education in Ghana is at comparable level to that of HDI and that of general education development in particular⁵³. Poverty in Ghana decreases when education equips students with both knowledge and practical skills. Kwame Akyeampong, Jerome Djangmah, Abena Oduro, Alhassan Seidu, and Frances Hunt emphasized that, Ghana Poverty Reduction Strategy II (GPRS II), shifts emphasis away from simply achieving poverty reduction, towards accelerating economic growth first by improving access and quality of basic education provision. Whereas GPRS I set targets for improving and achieving a sixyear basic education for all children up to 12 years, GPRS II proposed eventually making school attendance obligatory for all children age 4 to 15. This reflects the extension of the meaning of basic education as expressed in the government White Paper on education reforms⁵⁴.

⁵¹ Adu-Ababio and Osei, *Effects of an Education Reform*, P. 9 – 10

⁵² Adu-Ababio and Osei, *Effects of an Education Reform*, P. 11

⁵³ Lawrence Kofi Ameteepe and Dimitris Anastasiou, "Special and Inclusive Education in Ghana: Status and Progress, Challenges and Implications," *International Journal of Educational Development* 41 (2015), p 143 –144

⁵⁴ Kwame Akyeampong, Jerome Djangmah, Abena Oduro, Alhassan Seidu, and Frances Hunt, *Access to Basic Education in Ghana: The Evidence and the Issues*, Version 1 (Brighton, UK: University of Sussex, 2007), p. 73

Recommendations

In my point of view To effectively reduce poverty through education in Ghana, several measures can be undertaken. First, increasing access to quality education is essential. Enrollment opportunities should be expanded at all levels, particularly in rural and underserved areas, while ensuring gender equality in access, with special attention to girls and children with disabilities. Strengthening vocational and technical education is also crucial. Programs should be developed to align with labor market demands, equipping youth with practical skills, while entrepreneurship training should be promoted to empower communities and create local employment opportunities. Investing in teacher training and school resources is another priority. Continuous professional development for teachers can improve teaching quality, and schools must have adequate infrastructure, learning materials, and digital tools to enhance learning outcomes. Promoting inclusive education policies is also important. This includes implementing disability-friendly infrastructure and learning environments, as well as supporting scholarship and financial aid programs to reduce dropout rates due to poverty. Integrating digital literacy and modern technology into the curriculum at all levels can prepare students for the digital economy, while ensuring equitable access to affordable internet and digital learning tools. Supporting community and adult education programs is equally vital. Expanding literacy programs, vocational training, and awareness campaigns for adults, along with engaging communities in local development initiatives, can reinforce education's role in poverty reduction. Finally, monitoring and evaluating educational reforms is necessary to ensure effectiveness. Regular assessments of policies, such as the Free Senior High School program, should be conducted, and data on gender, disability, and rural-urban disparities should be collected to inform policy adjustments and improve overall educational outcomes.

Conclusion

Education plays a critical role in reducing poverty in Ghana by improving skills, increasing income opportunities, and promoting social mobility. Access to quality education at all levels—from primary to tertiary and vocational training—empowers individuals and communities, fosters gender equality, and addresses intergenerational poverty. Government policies, such as the Free Senior High School program and adult literacy initiatives, have made significant progress, but challenges remain, including disparities in rural areas, limited resources, and barriers for children with disabilities. Overall, investing in inclusive, equitable, and quality education is essential for sustainable economic development and poverty alleviation in Ghana.

Ethical Considerations

this research is based solely on secondary sources . However, several ethical principles still guide the study. First, all sources are properly cited using Chicago style to acknowledge authors' intellectual property and avoid plagiarism. Second, the analysis aims to represent the original authors' work accurately, without misinterpretation or selective use of evidence. Third, the research avoids cultural bias by respecting Ghana's social, economic, and educational context and by relying on reputable academic and institutional sources .

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